

Thioketonic Esters. Part II.

BY SUSIL KUMAR MITRA.

The method of the synthesis of thioketonic esters by the action of alcoholic potassium hydrosulphide on the corresponding unsaturated chloro-ester is not satisfactory as the yield is small due to loss of H_2S . In the preparation of ethyl thioacetoacetate (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 471) by this method, the main product is a heavy oil boiling at $155^\circ/15$ mm. The high boiling liquid is given the formula $C_{12}H_{18}O_4S$ from its molecular weight determination and has probably the following constitution as suggested by considerations given below.

(1) It does not give any lead salt, gives no coloration with ferric chloride and does not decolourise alcoholic solution of iodine, hence the absence of a thiol group.

(2) Its inertness towards phenylhydrazine shows the absence of a thioketonic group.

(3) On treating it with alcoholic potash in the cold and acidifying a dark red oil is obtained which on esterification gives a considerable quantity of ethyl thioacetoacetate.

Pure ethyl thioacetoacetate on boiling with alcoholic hydrochloric acid or traces of piperidine is converted into this product with

evolution of sulphuretted 'hydrogen. This fact naturally suggests the formation of the compound in the method already described to be due to unreacted potassium hydrosulphide; the effect of which is most probably like piperidine on ethyl thioacetoacetate. The yield of ethyl thioacetoacetate is increased by adding alcoholic solution of potassium hydrosulphide (KSH absolutely free from KOH) over benzene solution of ethyl chlorocrotonate.

Thioketonic esters, *e.g.*, ethyl thioacetoacetate, ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate have now been prepared in good yield without the formation of any by-product by passing H_2S into an alcoholic solution of the β ketonic esters, saturated with HCl gas. The reaction evidently takes place in the enol phase as otherwise polymerised products would result as suggested by Fromm and his collaborators (*Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 2600; 1891, **24**, 1457; *et seq.*). The thioketonic esters are purified by the decomposition of their lead salts in alcoholic suspension with H_2S .

Ethyl thiocetone dicarboxylate forms sodium derivative and the alkyl derivatives have been prepared by means of alkyl iodides in alcoholic sodium ethoxide diluted with benzene. The alkylated products are *S*-ethers; they do not form any lead salt; do not decolourise iodine nor give any coloration with ferric chloride and do not evolve H_2S on treatment with phenylhydrazine. The sodium derivative has evidently structure $C \begin{array}{c} | \\ -SNa \\ || \end{array}$ and that C:S group can impart negative character to the methylene group in close proximity becomes conclusive.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl thioacetoacetate from ethyl chlorocrotonate. (Modified method).—(A) An alcoholic solution of potassium hydrosulphide (24 g.), prepared by passing H_2S over balls of potassium in ether suspension, is added drop by drop into a benzene solution of ethyl chlorocrotonate (50 g.) at $48-50^\circ$, the solution being mechanically stirred. The benzene solution is washed with water and dehydrated. The oil obtained after removal of benzene, gives with freshly precipitated lead oxide yellow lead salt of ethyl thioacetoacetate. Pure ethyl thioacetoacetate is obtained by decomposing the lead salt in alcoholic suspension with H_2S , b. p. $75-80^\circ/12$ mm. Pyrazolone, m. p. 127° . Yield 50%.

Ethyl β -thiodicrotonate is obtained as a by-product in the preparation of ethylthioacetoacetate by means of alcoholic potassium hydrosulphide obtained either from caustic potash or from metallic potassium, even if the reaction is performed in benzene solution. The alcoholic wash of the lead salt is diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on dehydration is distilled in vacuum, when ethyl thiodicrotonate distils at $155^{\circ}/15$ mm. (Found: C, 55.5 ; H, 7.2 ; S, 12.1 ; M. W., 254 (cryoscopic in benzene). $C_{12}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 55.8 ; H, 6.9 ; S, 12.4 per cent; M. W., 258). The identical compound can also be obtained by boiling on water-bath an alcoholic solution of ethyl thioacetoacetate containing 1% HCl or trace of piperidine, till evolution of H_2S ceases. Yield 50%.

Ethyl thioacetoacetate can be obtained from this ester. The ester (50 g.) is dissolved in alcoholic potash (40 g. in 200 c.c.) in the cold and the red solution, on keeping for 2 days is acidified. The dark liquid, obtained after extraction with ether and dehydration over calcium chloride, is dissolved in alcohol (200 c.c.), the solution saturated with HCl at 0° and the ester formed is isolated in the usual manner. It is finally purified through lead salt and pure ethyl thioacetoacetate obtained in an yield of 10 g.

(B) *From ethyl acetoacetate*, H_2S gas is slowly passed into a solution of ethyl acetoacetate (100 g.) in alcohol (150 c.c.) saturated with HCl gas at 0° . On standing for 10 hours, crushed ice (2 lbs.) is poured into the solution, the ester extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with dilute sodium carbonate and the ether evaporated off. The rose-red oil is dissolved in rectified spirit and the solution added in thin stream over freshly precipitated lead oxide at 0° with vigorous stirring and the lead salt decomposed with H_2S in alcoholic suspension and the ester extracted with ether and distilled in vacuum at $75-80^{\circ}/12$ mm, yield 85%. It forms with phenylhydrazine the pyrazolone (m.p. 127°) described previously (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 471).

Ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate is obtained by passing H_2S gas for 8 hours into an alcoholic solution of ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (50 g. in 100 c.c.), saturated with HCl. The solution is treated with ice, the ester extracted with benzene and the benzene layer washed with dilute sodium carbonate and the benzene removed under reduced pressure. It is finally purified by preparing the lead salt as in the previous case and decomposing it with H_2S . Yield 75%.

It is a rose-red sweet-smelling oil, decomposing at $128^{\circ}/15$ mm. with evolution of H_2S producing an oil which does not contain sulphur. It decolourises iodine, produces green coloration with $FeCl_3$ and evolves H_2S very energetically with phenylhydrazine. (Found: C, 49.4 ; H, 6.8; S, 14.5. $C_9H_{14}O_4S$ requires C, 49.5 ; H, 6.4 ; S, 14.6 per cent).

Propyl thioacetone dicarboxylic ethyl ester.—Ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate (10 g.) is dissolved in the cold in alcohol (30 c.c.) containing sodium (1 g.) and treated with propyl iodide (9 g.) and benzene (30 c.c.). The solution on keeping over night is heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. The oil which separates on adding water is extracted with benzene and the solution dehydrated and distilled in vacuum and the ester collected at $220^{\circ}/30$ mm. (Found: C, 55.2 ; H, 8.3 ; S, 11.97. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4S$ requires C, 55.3 ; H, 7.7 ; S, 12.3 per cent).

Ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylic ethyl ester is obtained by the interaction of ethyl bromide with ethyl thioacetone dicarboxylate as above. It boils at $175^{\circ}/17$ mm. (Found: C, 53.3 ; H, 7.7 ; S, 12.7. $C_{11}H_{18}O_4S$ requires C, 53.6 ; H, 7.3 ; S, 13.0 per cent).

The alkylated esters are colourless liquids possessing garlic odour. They are very stable and can be even boiled under atmospheric pressure with slight decomposition.

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